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Experiences of Non-Social Science Majors Teaching Social Science Subjects

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Abstract – This study determines the experiences of non-social science majors teaching social science subjects. Utilizing a descriptive-narrative research method, it delved into the intricacies of individuals' lives by gathering personal stories and examining their significance. Respondents comprised five (5) junior and senior high school teachers from St. Paul University Surigao, during the 2023-2024 school year, in which each teacher was purposefully chosen to participate in the study, ensuring representation from those outside their specialized field. The study concludes that out-of-field teaching is a common occurrence in schools yet there is little action done to address this even in a private school like St. Paul University Surigao. In cases such as these, the initial reactions of the teachers assigned a non-major subject to teach is anxiety, doubts, and hesitation of being able to teach effectively a subject that is not their expertise. In which when this happens, the teachers do their best to find resources, search the internet, and find help from their colleagues in order to at least understand the subject that they are going to teach which also shows their openness in teaching the subject. During teaching the subject, they find that social science is relatable however, there are instances where there are terms or even lessons in which they find hard to comprehend.

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INTRODUCTION

Social sciences are crucial for understanding societal dynamics, fostering critical thinking, and promoting responsible citizenship and democratic participation. Teaching these subjects equips students with the knowledge and skills to navigate societal structures and issues, while also instilling civic values and encouraging engaged, responsible citizenship, thus making education more relevant and impactful. To do so effectively, teachers need subject-specific knowledge, including content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, as well as the ability to apply that knowledge to manage demanding classroom situations (Jeschke et al., 2021).

However, when teachers are required to teach subjects outside their specialization, it adds to their burden, stress, and reduces productivity, which can hinder student learning. Public and private school teachers are highly capable and competent, thanks to their degrees, licenses or certificates, diplomas, and skill sets. Yet, challenges arise when there is a mismatch in their knowledge, preventing them from optimizing the teaching and learning process. This mismatch can lead to dysfunctional behavior, reduced job satisfaction, and a lack of interest in the subject, further exacerbating turnover issues and instructional challenges (Augusto Jr., 2019 as cited by Layese et al., 2024).

In the recent K to 12 Program, the implementation of Senior High School has faced new challenges due to a shortage of teachers, particularly in provinces where few teachers have majored in social studies or social sciences. As a result, teachers from different majors often find themselves teaching social sciences. This study aims to describe and investigate the real-world experiences of these teachers.

In the school, the researchers have observed the same phenomenon happening among them where Filipino, TLE, or even Mathematics majors are tasked to teach Junior High School *Araling Panlipunan* or major Social Science subjects for Humanities and Social Sciences in Senior High School. For these reasons, the researchers were prompted to conduct this study where it aims to describe and investigate the real-world experiences of teachers instructing students in subjects outside their area of expertise. This study will be beneficial for school administrators in planning teacher training programs by highlighting the challenges and needs of teachers teaching outside their areas of expertise. It will also provide valuable insights for teachers who find themselves in such situations, helping them to navigate and improve their teaching strategies and effectiveness. Additionally, it will inform curriculum developers about the importance of aligning teacher expertise with subject assignments to enhance educational outcomes.

Statement of the Problem

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This study aims to determine the experiences of non-social science majors teaching social science subjects. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the real-life experiences of non-social science majors in teaching social science subjects in terms of their;
 - 1.1. feelings;
 - 1.2. support;
 - 1.3. challenges; and
 - 1.4. coping solutions?
2. What are the advantages and disadvantages of teaching a non-major subject?
3. What are the strengths and weaknesses of teaching a non-major subject?
4. Based on the results and discussion, what recommendations may be proposed?

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

In the realm of education, teaching serves as a cornerstone not only for students' academic progress but also for their moral, spiritual, and psychological growth. Rooted in a deeply humanistic approach, teaching is guided by qualifications, standards, and accountability, all revolving around a profound understanding of students' needs. Teachers shoulder the responsibility of nurturing their students' learning, ensuring they grasp essential knowledge. However, some educators find themselves instructing subjects beyond their expertise, a phenomenon termed out-of-field teaching.

Out-of-field teaching emerges when teachers are assigned to deliver lessons in subjects where they lack specific qualifications or proficiency. This scenario is common in both public and private educational institutions, often due to decisions made by school administrators or government recruitment practices (Du Plessis, 2015 as cited by Raymundo, 2021). Research by Caldis (2017) suggests that many teachers encounter out-of-field teaching early in their careers, disrupting subject integrity and leading to student disengagement, lower academic achievement, and diminished teacher confidence.

Student achievement, often seen as a reflection of effective teaching, is closely tied to educators' competence. Quality education, as perceived through this lens, contrasts with the notion of the "good teacher" adhering strictly to professional standards. Effective teaching entails delivering content that meets disciplinary standards and employing methods that are appropriate and morally just, ultimately enhancing students' subject proficiency (Zuzovsky, 2009 as cited by Raymundo, 2021).

An analysis conducted by (Cortes, Pineda, & Jugar, 2019 as cited by Barbadillo, 2021) suggests that the current teacher education curriculum and hiring processes in Senior High School (SHS) in the Philippines contribute to the prevalence of out-of-field teaching. This mismatch between teacher education and the needs of SHS strands, including academic, sports, arts and design, and TVL, exacerbates the situation. Further studies by (Pacaña, Ramos, Catarata, & Inocian, 2019 as cited by

Barbadillo, 2021) and (Attia, 2017 as cited by Barbadillo, 2021) reinforce these findings, highlighting the challenges faced by out-of-field teachers and their impact on instructional quality and teacher morale.

To address the issue, schools have implemented various strategies, including seminars on social studies teaching and fostering harmonious working relationships among colleagues. Many out-of-field teachers also turn to experienced peers for guidance, demonstrating the importance of collaborative learning environments. Additionally, the introduction of the Culture-based Bayle Teaching Model (BTM) aims to enhance learning outcomes by leveraging the expertise of subject area specialists and school administrators. Supporting these teachers, whether through discipline-specific professional development or mentoring, is essential, as emphasized by (Shah et al., 2019). Such efforts can bolster subject-matter competence and pedagogical content knowledge, ultimately improving teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes.

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a descriptive-narrative research method, delving into the intricacies of individuals' lives by gathering personal stories and examining their significance. Respondents comprised five (5) junior and senior high school teachers from St. Paul University Surigao, Surigao del Norte, during the 2023-2024 school year, specifically selected for their non-major roles in teaching social science subjects. Each teacher was purposefully chosen to participate in the study, ensuring representation from those outside their specialized field. Through the administration of a 15-30 minute questionnaire, the study delved into the lived experiences of these educators, uncovering the challenges they faced, the strategies they employed to overcome them, and the pros and cons of teaching subjects outside their expertise. Data collection involved the distribution of questionnaires containing open-ended inquiries, facilitating a fluid exploration of the topic. Responses were meticulously recorded and analyzed, employing the constant comparison method to identify recurring themes and conceptual categories derived from the discussions. Ultimately, the study provided valuable insights into the realities of teaching non-major subjects, shedding light on both the rewards and the hurdles encountered in this endeavor.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Real-life Experiences of the Teacher-Respondents as to their:

A. Feelings

Different feelings were felt by the respondents when they were tasked at teaching a subject in which they do not specialized on. Their initial reaction involved feeling anxious, nervous, and not confident at all at the task at hand. Teacher A states that, “*At first, I felt nervous, anxious, and not confident in teaching AP since this is not my major but I learned from it and deliver it well later on*”.

Teacher A’s statement implies a positive learning experience and personal growth. Initially feeling nervous, anxious, and lacking confidence in teaching Araling Panlipunan (AP) due to it not being

their major, the individual later gained confidence and proficiency in delivering the subject effectively. This suggests that through perseverance and experience, they were able to overcome initial challenges and develop their skills in teaching AP. This was also asserted by the others in which Teacher D states, *“At first I was not confident about teaching these subjects. . . Though Social Science is not aligned with my college degree, it is not as hard as I initially thought”* and Teacher E also states, *“It is very challenging experience since it is not related to my subjects however, it is also fun because I was able to learn new things”*.

These statements suggest that initially, they harbored doubts and felt anxious about their ability to teach the subject. However, upon attempting to teach it, they discovered that they were gradually becoming more proficient. The teachers also show willingness to teach a new subject in which according to Teacher B, *“When the subject (was) introduced to me, I was a bit hesitant but at the same time excited what would be the outcome and started to search on strategies on how to deal with the subject to be engaging”*. This is a good indication since according to the study by Herawati et al.,(2022), the teachers' willingness towards change is an excellent mediating variable for self-efficacy in influencing professional competence.

B. Support

The study unveils that teachers receive personal and emotional support from both their colleagues and their subject team leader. Respondents indicated that this support assists them in alleviating stress and concerns associated with teaching subjects in which they lack sufficient expertise. Teacher A states, *“I got support by my STL and got other learning materials”* and Teacher D also states, *“My colleagues have also been supportive and ready to help out when I need some clarifications”*. This presents a positive sign as highlighted by Prilleltensky (2012) as referenced in an article by DeAngelis (2012) on the American Psychological Association website, emphasizing the significance of providing support to teachers. Upon entering the classroom, teachers frequently experience feelings of solitude and isolation, compounded by a shortage of practical resources and essential knowledge required for effective classroom management.

C. Challenges

It is commonly understood that challenges are integral to growth and transformation. By facing and overcoming challenges, individuals develop enhanced capabilities and skills across various domains. As revealed by Teacher A, *“One of the challenges are some topics of the Araling Panlipunan subject in Grade 9 are hard and I had difficulties on it. Teacher C also states that, “One of the challenges is the diverse needs of each students. They come from varied backgrounds and experiences which makes it challenging”*. As revealed in the data of Schools and Staffing Surveys (SASS), indicate that out-of-field teaching in subjects is common in both public and private high schools. It is for this reason that teachers

should be equipped with different strategies and techniques in teaching. Teachers should portray as facilitators of learning in every aspect (Raymundo, 2021).

D. Coping Solutions

The teacher establishes a foundation for each student to gain essential knowledge and skills, taking into account the diverse needs of learners and educational settings. To effectively address challenges encountered in teaching, teachers must possess a repertoire of strategies and techniques tailored to various situations. Teacher A reveals that, “*My coping solution from it were to study in advance and find more learning materials from the internet*”. This was also done by Teacher B in which she stated that, “*What I did was research on the topics in order to familiarize the content that learners would be able to understand and can relate to especially since social science needs to be related to social issues and environment*”. In this case, the rise of technology greatly influences the educational process, with non-specialist teachers finding support in meeting the demands of teaching. On the other hand, the assistant coming from the co-teacher is one of the coping solutions that best help the respondents. Good relationships and communication were established among the parties. As Teacher D mentioned, “*My colleagues have also been supportive and ready to help out when I need some clarifications*”.

Based on the journal article published by Arkansas State University (2017) as cited by Raymundo (2021), research suggests that today’s teachers and school administrators are more interested in teacher collaboration than the previous generation. The proponents of teacher collaboration believed that teachers working together have a positive impact on each other and contribute naturally to school improvement.

Advantages and Disadvantages of Teaching a Non-Major Subject

Teaching non-major subjects presents opportunities for professional growth as educators expand their knowledge base and develop new skills in diverse areas. However, according to Raymundo (2021), this endeavor often demands additional time and effort to ensure effective lesson delivery tailored to meet the specific needs of learners outlined in the curriculum. As presented in table 1 below, these are the advantages and disadvantages of teaching a non-major subject as perceived by the teacher-respondents:

Table 1. Advantages and Disadvantages of Teaching a Non-Major Subject as Perceived by the Teacher-Respondents

Teacher-Respondent	Advantages	Disadvantages
A	The language used is also Filipino which is also my major.	Some of the topics are hard to understand so I really need to study on it in advance.
B	I am able to learn new things or unfamiliar lessons.	I might divert my interest which is not aligned with my subject or course.
C	It can help test my versatility and can broaden my perspective by being exposed to a different field.	I might be less motivated/interested to teach in a non-major subject which can affect their performance.
D	Helps me in gaining more knowledge about social science and helps me become more interested in the discipline.	I feel less-confident sometimes and it takes a lot of time to master the topic.
E	Gain more insight about the social sciences.	Takes a lot of time for me to master the terms used in the discipline and sometime, I have to go back to the basics.

The participants' responses shed light on the challenges of mastering non-major subjects, emphasizing the significant time and effort needed. This difficulty is compounded by the necessity for teachers to excel in their specialized fields while also learning additional subjects. As cited by Raymundo (2021), Fe Rosalinda R. Caylao (2015), a school principal in San Fernando, Pampanga, expressed concern about hiring teachers for non-specialized subjects. She stated, *“as a public secondary principal for almost five years, it pains me to see that teachers are being hired to teach not their subject of specialization. Besides while it is true that principals are supposed to be instructional leaders, we cannot deny the fact that we have to exert double effort time in teaching our teachers the content, competencies, innovative teaching strategies, assessment, and everything there is to learn in a particular subject especially for out-of-field teachers.* These insights reflect the personal experiences of the participants during their teaching practices.

Strengths and Weaknesses of Teaching a Non-Major Subject

Exploring the strengths and weaknesses of teaching non-major subjects offers valuable insights into the challenges and benefits faced by teachers in diverse educational settings. This table provides a comprehensive overview of the experiences and perspectives of teachers grappling with the demands of teaching subjects outside their area of expertise. By examining the responses gathered from teachers, we can gain a deeper understanding of the complexities involved in mastering non-major subjects and the strategies employed to navigate these challenges.

Table 2. Strengths and Weaknesses of Teaching a Non-Major Subject as Perceived by the Teacher-Respondents

Teacher-Respondent	Strengths	Weaknesses
A	Its content were realistic so I had the opportunity to share towards the students my insights about a particular topic.	There are content or topic that only a social science major can relate while the non-major teachers had a hard time understanding.
B	I can introduce other aspects/ topics which will be interesting for the students that can generate curiosity and be able to applied in their personal lives.	It is sometimes hard to answer some of the questions of the students.
C	It helps me apply innovative teaching methods in order to increase student engagement.	I fear that I lack expertise in a non-major subject which can affect the quality of my teaching.
D	Since the subject is new to me, I am more motivated to learn the subject which helps me develop my personal growth. It also encourages me to be more creative in teaching.	It is hard to assess the students sometimes especially when I myself am not too confident about teaching the subject.
E	It is relatable and because of that I can give real-life examples.	There are terms in which I have to search the internet first before I am able to understand what it means.

The table revealed the different perceptions of the respondents on the strength and weaknesses that they experienced in teaching the non-major subject. Through their experiences, and identified weaknesses the respondent find their ways to address their weaknesses and convert them into their strength. Those challenges and trials help them to become a better teacher. Ingersoll (2000) as cited by Raymundo (2021) implies in his article in ERIC Digest that the phenomenon of out-of-field teaching – teachers teaching subjects for which have little education or training – has long been a crucial but relatively unrecognized problem in schools. It is a crucial issue because highly qualified teachers may in actuality become highly unqualified if they are assigned to teach subjects for which they have little training or education. Fulgado (2020) in her paper reiterates that there are problems encountered by the non-specialists in delivering their lessons and they make adjustments to cope with the challenge in teaching the subjects that are not their area of specialization, thus they are flexible in teaching the mismatched subjects. It implies that even a teacher is qualified to teach but the subject is not suited to its specialty, problems might arise and can affect teachers, mentally, physically, and emotionally.

CONCLUSION

Out-of-field teaching is a common occurrence in schools yet there is little action done to address this even in a private school like St. Paul University Surigao. In cases such as these, the initial reactions of the teachers assigned a non-major subject to teach is anxiety, doubts, and hesitation of being able to teach effectively a subject that is not their expertise. In which when this happens, the teachers do their best to find resources, search the internet, and find help from their colleagues in order to at least understand the subject that they are going to teach which also shows their openness in teaching the subject. During teaching the subject, they find that social science is relatable however, there are instances where there are terms or even lessons in which they find hard to comprehend.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based from the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations were suggested:

1. It is recommended that the school administrators give the teachers assigned a non-major subject ample time to prepare themselves to teach the subject.
2. May the school also offer continuous professional development opportunities focused on out-of-field teaching strategies, instructional technologies, and subject-specific knowledge enhancement, and also to provide funding support for teachers to attend conferences, workshops, and courses relevant to their teaching assignments.

3. May the school encourage the establishment of support systems within the school, such as peer mentoring networks, instructional coaching programs, and academic support centers, to provide personalized assistance and guidance to teachers facing challenges in teaching non-major subjects.
4. It is also recommended that the school ensure that teachers have access to a wide range of resources, including textbooks, online databases, educational websites, and professional journals, to support their learning and teaching efforts. Establish a centralized repository of resources specifically curated for out-of-field teaching to streamline access and promote efficiency.

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